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METHODS OF STEP-BY-STEP ORTHOPEDIC REHABILITATION IN PATIENTS WITH MAXILLARY DEFECTS

Boymuradov Sh.A., Ruziyeva S.S

Tashkent State Medical University

ABSTRACT

To study the effectiveness of using various removable maxillary prostheses (including hollow and implant-retained types) at different stages of orthopedic rehabilitation in patients with complete postoperative maxillary defects. After COVID-19 infection, some patients continue to experience various complications in the maxillofacial region, including the development of jaw defects. These conditions negatively affect the physical, functional, and psycho-emotional state of patients, reducing their quality of life. The purpose of this study is to assess the quality of life of patients with jaw defects in the post-COVID period. Clinical and sociological methods were used in the study.

Keywords: *osteonecrosis, resection, dental implants, osteonecrosis, clamps, autograft, pustotely, former, bridge.*

Introduction

Extensive acquired defects in the upper jaw—that is, defects that open into the maxillary sinus (maxillary sinus) or nasal cavity—lead to severe impairment of chewing, breathing, speech (open nasal speech), and swallowing functions. If there is a hole in the upper jaw, a replacement prosthesis (prosthesis-obturator) is made, which fills it, that is, has an obturating part. The main problem is the fixation of the prosthesis, which is made after resection (i.e., removal of part of the jaw) [10]. One of the factors

that makes fixation difficult is that air from the inside, when breathing through the nose, exerts pressure on the prosthesis and displaces it. In addition, teeth that remain on only one side of the jaw cannot hold the prosthesis well. Another factor that impairs the fixation of the prosthesis is the large size of the defect being repaired and, as a result, the weight of the prosthesis increases. Large defects in the alveolar part (the area where the tooth roots are located) lead to the indentation of the facial soft tissues (cheek or lip). In order to reduce the mass of the prosthesis, it is made split or hollow. Another important aspect when choosing a prosthetic design is the timing of the tumor removal surgery. Depending on when the resection (removal of part of the jaw) is performed, the following types of prosthetics are distinguished:

Direct prosthetics - the prosthesis is prepared before the operation and installed during the operation, directly on the operating table.

Early prosthetics - the prosthesis is prepared and installed after surgery, after the stitches have healed and the postoperative swelling has decreased, that is, after scarring has begun.

Late (i.e., long-term) prosthetics are performed after the wound surface has completely healed.

The use of dental implants to correct dental row defects is an effective method of treating patients with partial or complete loss of teeth. Modern implantology is a direction in the development of more advanced dental implant designs that evenly distribute the load on the surrounding bone tissue and optimize the processes of osteointegration (the process of fusion of the implant and bone).

Materials and methods:

The object of the study were patients diagnosed with COVID-19 infection and a defect in the jawbone in the post-COVID period. The study involved male and female patients over 18 years of age. Patients were selected from among those observed in the dental and maxillofacial surgical departments. The patients were divided into two groups.

The main group - patients with a jaw defect in the post-COVID period.

Control group - healthy individuals who have not had or have had COVID-19 infection, but have not been diagnosed with a jaw defect.

It was established that COVID-19 infection in patients was confirmed by PCR or serological methods. The jaw bone defect was clinically and radiologically confirmed.

Results

The face is clearly scarred with asymmetry. The left cheek is sunken, dense, with limited mobility. The lips are closed crookedly, the mouth is difficult to open and incomplete. According to the patient, the quality of life has deteriorated sharply, as he works as a school teacher and can no longer perform his professional activities.

After resection of half of the left upper jaw, a defect of alveolar and palatal growths measuring 6×5 cm was formed at the level of the nasal area.

Picture 1. Patient A with osteonecrosis of the maxilla, granulations are visible, mucous membrane hyperemic (reddened) and swollen.

In the remaining jaw, the dentition defects were restored with a metal-ceramic bridge prosthesis resting on teeth 1.1, 1.3, 1.4 and 1.7, which is in satisfactory condition. The remaining part of the hard palate is flat (pic. 1). The patient required anti-inflammatory therapy, and the defect was tamponed with sterile gauze pads.

In the early prosthetic phase, a metal-based partial denture was prepared. The metal base was cast based on a duplicate model. The prosthesis is secured to the entire cast using abutment-retaining clasps. These clasps tightly surround the teeth, and occlusal overlays help to evenly distribute chewing pressure.

The metal base makes the prosthesis more durable, since the defect being repaired is large. Since the wound is not completely closed, the obturator (closing) part of the prosthesis is not inserted deeply into the defect.

After the prosthesis was installed, its satisfactory fixation, restoration of speech, ability to eat, and proper breathing were noted. The patient was taught how to properly insert and remove the prosthesis. The patient was introduced to the features of the oral cavity, the adaptation of the prosthesis to the prosthesis, and recommendations were given for oral and prosthetic care.

After 8 months, during the examination, it was noted that the surgical site was completely healed. The patient constantly uses the prosthesis, adheres to the recommended hygiene rules. He notes that speech and breathing have been restored. However, during eating, he experiences some difficulty due to the prosthesis moving into the defect area and liquid food flowing under the prosthesis.

To prevent the resection prosthesis (that is, the prosthesis that is placed after removing part of the upper jaw) from falling out, a support is created in the defect. This support is provided by the connection of the prosthesis with any anatomical structure that can serve as a solid support. To reduce the displacement of the prosthesis in the vertical direction, its mass is reduced, that is, the prosthesis is made hollow (hollow). On this basis, a prosthesis with a light and hollow obturation part that enters the defect was prepared. The hollow resection prosthesis prepared in this way has a clearly defined obturation (filling) part in the form of a “mushroom”, which easily enters the defect cavity, prevents the prosthesis from moving and ensures its stability during functions (for example, chewing, speaking, breathing).

The installation of a prosthesis involves a number of testing steps: sealing (i.e., air and fluid tightness of the oral cavity), occlusal relationships (closure of teeth), fixation, etc.

The main signs that indicate a hermetic closure of the oral cavity are: restoration of speech and the disappearance of an open nasal tone (hoarseness), as well as the fact that liquid food does not pass into the nasopharynx when ingested. The degree of

separation of the oral cavity from the nasal cavity is also assessed by tilting the head and rinsing the mouth with water: if water does not enter the nose, then the oral and nasal cavities are well separated.

In addition, the patient should be able to puff out their cheeks and at this time, air should not escape through the nose, and the mouth should be able to open freely.

During the fitting process, the patient was taught how to properly wear the prosthesis, as well as given recommendations on proper oral and prosthetic care and the use of hygiene products. These measures have yielded positive results, as confirmed by the sealing and fixation tests conducted. For several years, the patient successfully used a hollow, removable prosthesis, but due to the large size of the obturator part, she experienced some discomfort when putting on and taking off the prosthesis. The young woman was especially dissatisfied with her appearance, since the prosthesis only slightly improved her appearance, and due to the coarse scarring of the facial soft tissues, complete lip closure was not preserved. Initially, the defect on the left side of the upper jaw was closed using an autograft consisting of bone-muscle-skin taken from the lower leg (leg). As a further stage of rehabilitation, the patient was given implants.

The improvement of surgical restoration methods, as well as their effectiveness, requires high-precision diagnostics, planning and placement. The success of implantation depends, first of all, on careful planning and correct implementation of the treatment. This requires close cooperation between orthopedists and surgeons, teamwork, ensuring accurate preparation of the surgical stage. Planning an implant-based prosthesis is an important problem from a functional and aesthetic point of view.

The surgical-orthopedic phase lasted more than two years. During this period, time was required for the autograft to heal, the implants to be placed, and the gingival formers to be placed. During this time, the patient used a temporary partial denture with a plate.

Finally, a permanent partial removable prosthesis with good hammer (hammer-shaped) fixation to the implants placed in the bone was prepared. At the same time, plastic surgeons also did a great job: they reconstructed the left nostril, smoothed out

rough post-operative scars, restored the volume and elasticity of the soft tissues of the left half of the face. All this significantly improved the patient's appearance, psycho-emotional state and allowed him to return to work with primary school students.

Picture 2. Clinical condition after installation of formers

Conclusion

Large-scale surgical interventions are accompanied by the formation of defects, which in turn raises the issue of functional, cosmetic and social rehabilitation of patients. An important aspect in solving these goals is the preparation of a post-resection prosthesis taking into account the individual characteristics of the patient. These individual characteristics include the boundaries of the defect, the condition of the surrounding tissues and the patient himself.

The use of modern orthopedic and surgical rehabilitation methods, especially in oncological patients after unilateral resection of the upper jaw, allows achieving positive results in restoring the lost functions of the dento-maxillary system. This helps patients to more successfully adapt to society and return them to an active life.

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